

IPBES IAS assessment, data management report for Scenarios & Models Liaison.

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Description

A systematic literature review of the English literature has been conducted by the participants of the scenarios and models liaison group to analyse scenarios and models aspects of alien species for the IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control. The process was structured into four phases: (i) keyword selection, (ii) web search and reference extraction, (iii) initial screening for inclusion and exclusion, and (iv) extended literature review. The process overview is presented in figure 1 and each step will be explained in more detail below in the protocol section.

Protocol

(i) Keyword selection

The selection of keywords for the systematic literature review was dissected into targeted keyword compilations for the main themes of the review. First, we identified invasive alien species related keywords, focussing on different terms used to describe alien species in the scientific literature as well as keywords related to invaded habitats. The second set of keywords, addresses models and associated language related to model output. The third group of keywords is on scenarios and related outputs.

As baseline for the keywords, we used the publication by Buchadas et al. 2017¹. Subsequently, we started a participatory expert-based approach to identify missing keywords and strengthened the

¹ Ana Buchadas, Ana Sofia Vaz, João P. Honrado, Diogo Alagador, Rita Bastos, João A. Cabral, Mário Santos, Joana R. Vicente, Dynamic models in research and management of biological invasions, *Journal of Environmental Management*, Volume 196, 2017, Pages 594-606, ISSN 0301-4797, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.03.060>.

keyword selection, where all members of the liaison group were invited to review the provided list and suggest additional keywords. The final set of keywords is given in figure 2.

Figure 2: Final selection of keywords for the three relevant topics of the scenarios and models literature review of the invasive alien species assessment.

(ii) Web search and reference extraction

Based on the final set of keywords, search strings for ISI Web of Science and Scopus were built to extract the meta information (i.e., Authors, Title, Keywords, Abstract, doi) of all selected publications. No other filters (e.g., time constraints) to the search results were applied. Each extracted reference was given a

new identifier for internal processing. The results from the ISI Web of Science (<https://www.webofknowledge.com>) and Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>) search were then merged resulting in 49,816 records in total and 30,299 records after duplicates were removed (figure 3). Searches were performed on 1st of April 2020.

Figure 3: Overview of the records obtained from ISI Web of Science and Scopus by the scenarios and models literature review of the invasive alien species assessment.

(iii) Initial screening for inclusion and exclusion

The obtained 30,299 records were screened to decide if the publications are relevant for the systematic review. To be relevant, a reference needed to fulfil three criteria: (1) The reference addresses (invasive) alien species; (2) The reference addresses models; and (3) The reference addresses scenarios. We further excluded review papers, to avoid duplication of entries. These criteria were assessed based on the information provided in the title, keywords and abstract (except for review papers, these were as well excluded at the extended literature review stage). If the criteria were not clearly addressed in the title, keywords and abstracts, but they suggested that the reference is relevant, it was classified as “potentially relevant” and moved to the next stage in order to not omit important references. Additionally, during this stage we performed a search reliability check. For this, we ran a search in Google Scholar using very general keywords: “invasive species”, “models” and “scenarios”. We then

extracted the 50 first entries from this search and checked if they were included in our more targeted searches. OF the 50 records, 35 were already included in our database. Of the 15 records not included only 5 were of potential interest to our review, following the procedure outlined above. From that we concluded, that our search strings worked reasonably well.

This inclusion and exclusion process resulted in the exclusion of 28,457 records (including the 10 records from the reliability test) and the inclusion of 1857 records for the extended literature review.

(iv) Extended literature review

For the extended literature, we developed a template to extract the relevant information from the references. This template was developed in a collaborative effort among the liaison group experts, the lead authors of the chapters of the assessment and the coordinating lead authors of the assessment. The template included 5 overarching sections, with detailed categories of data extraction. The overarching topics related to: (i) geographic domain, (ii) IAS features, (iii) models features, (iv) scenarios features, and (v) cross cutting themes. A detailed list of the categories, the associated rationales and answer categories are given in table 1 and associated definitions for individual categories are provided at the end of the document.

Before starting the extended literature review, a consistency exercise among the 11 extended review participants was conducted to ensure that the reviewers classified the references similarly. Each participant had to classify the same five references using the developed template. Afterwards, Kappa, a consistency score, was calculated among the participants. The Kappa statistics across all reviewers was above 0.86.

Subsequently, the references were subdivided among the participants into equal tranches and processed accordingly. After completion by each participant, the information was merged into one complete dataset. The final dataset included 778 references, excluding another 1079 records that did not fit the scope of the review.

Analysis

The final database was used to perform descriptive analysis, visualizing the overall content of the database according to the five overarching topics. These descriptive analysis aimed to describe status quo as well as temporal information and to identify potential gaps in the scientific literature.

Additionally, we performed a multidimensional scaling cluster analysis (MDS) to identify clusters of categories that occur most commonly together in the scientific literature.

File

S&M_final references.txt

Table 1: Categories of the review template for the extended review, including the name of the category (category), the rationale behind the category (Definition/Rationale) and the possible answer types and categories (answer categories).

Category	Definition / Rationale	Answer categories
Paper ID	Unique ID given to each publication	
Reviewer ID	Reviewer Initials (see list above)	
Paper included in the review	Information if the paper fits all three criteria to be included in the review. Criteria for inclusion are: 1. The paper addresses (invasive) alien species 2. The paper addresses models 3. The paper addresses scenarios Additionally 4. Review papers have to be excluded! If you exclude a paper based on these criteria, the other categories do not need to be filled!	- yes - no
Country	Country where the study has been conducted. If the study has been conducted in more than one country, use the option “several”	- Several - Individual countries based on ISO definitions (See ISO definitions below)
IPBES regions	IPBES region where the study has been conducted Multiple answers are possible.	- Africa - The Americas - Asia and the Pacific - Europe and Central Asia - Antarctica - NS (not stated)
No. of IAS	Categorization if the paper refers to only one or multiple (invasive) alien species at once. If the paper addresses 2 or more species classify as “multispecies”.	- Individual - Multispecies - NS (not stated)
Taxa	Identification of the larger taxonomic group to which the taxa considered in the paper belong. Multiple answers are possible.	- Plants (including bryophytes) - Mammals - Reptiles - Amphibians - Fish - Invertebrates - Bacteria - Fungi

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Birds - NS (not stated)
IPBES Unit of Analysis	<p>IPBES Unit of Analysis considered in the study</p> <p>see Units of Analysis spreadsheet if needed</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Terrestrial - Marine - Freshwater - Anthroposized areas - NS (not stated)
Management (I)	<p>Is management included in the analysis of the study?</p> <p>If you answer “no”, “Management (II) & (III)” do not have to be filled.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - yes - no
Management (II)	<p>If management is included in the analysis of the study, which management actions are covered.</p> <p>Multiple answers are possible.</p> <p>If “other” please specify under “Management (III)”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prevention - Early detection - Eradication - Containment - Mitigation - Other - NS (not stated)
Management (III)	<p>If other in “Management (II)” please specify quoting the terminology used in the paper</p>	Open answer
Impacts (I)	<p>Are impacts (positive or negative) of IAS included in the analysis of the study</p> <p>If you answer “none”, “Impacts (II)” does not have to be filled.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - positive - negative - both - none
Impacts (II)	<p>If impacts are included in the analysis of the study, please indicate the name of the impact (positive or negative).</p> <p>Quote the terminology used in the paper</p>	Open answer
Pathways (I)	<p>Are pathways of species introduction included in the analysis of the study</p> <p>If you answer “no”, “Pathways (II) & (III)” do not have to be filled.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - yes - no
Pathways (II)	<p>If pathways of introduction are included in the analysis of the study, please indicate which pathways.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Release in nature - Escape from confinement - Transport – Contaminant - Transport – Stowaway

	<p>Answer options follow the CBD terminology.</p> <p>If “other” please specify under “Pathways (III)”</p> <p>Multiple answers are possible.</p> <p>For more information on relevant sub-categories see pathways definition below!</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Corridor - Unaided
Pathways (III)	<p>If other in “Pathways (II)” please specify quoting the terminology used in the paper</p>	<p>Open answer</p>
Extent	<p>The extent the model is applied on in the study</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protected areas - Sub-national - National - International (>2 countries) - Continental - Global
Spatial Output	<p>Does the model provide spatially explicit output data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - yes - no
Temporal Output	<p>Are the outputs dynamic (e.g., outputs for every hour/month/year, ...) or static</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Static - Dynamic
Model type (I)	<p>Model technique classifications based on a previous IPBES report. If you cannot classify the model please fill this field as DK (don't know) but please add the most information as possible in the 3.6 field (copy paste information presented in the model description)</p> <p>For more information see model type definitions below!</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expert-based systems - Correlative models - Process-based models - Hybrid models (combining correlative and process-based models) - NS (not stated) - DK (don't know)
Model type (II)	<p>If Dk in “Model type (I)” please provide information on the model from the paper.</p>	<p>Open answer</p>
Evaluation / Validation	<p>Identify if the model has been “evaluated” and/or “validated” in the study</p> <p>Evaluation = Accuracy of the model based on data applied in the model</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - yes - no

	<p>calibration</p> <p>Validation = Accuracy of the model based on independent data not included in the model calibration</p>	
Predictor interactions	Identify if interactions among predictor variables are considered in the model (e.g., the interaction of climate and land use)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - yes - no
Response variable (I)	<p>What is modelled as response variable in the model</p> <p>Multiple answers are possible.</p> <p>If “other” please specify under “Response variable (II)”.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Species richness - Species abundance - Impacts - Species distribution - Other
Response variable (II)	If other in “Response variable (I)” please specify quoting the terminology used in the paper	Open answer
Scenario Type (I)	<p>Exploratory scenarios = Storylines exploring a range of possible futures <i>Example:</i> Studies using RCP or SSP scenarios generally are exploratory as they project based on current knowledge into the future which is defined by a set of drivers (e.g., Climate from the RCPs or socio-economic trends from the SSPs) → e.g., classical Species Distribution Models where a study explores how a species distribution changes under climate change</p> <p>Target-seeking scenarios = Storylines that develop pathways to a specific predefined target <i>Example:</i> Climate Change studies that assess potential pathways to reach the 1.5°C global warming target. This target/goal is explicitly stated in the study (e.g.: van Vuuren et al. 2018; https://doi-org.uaccess.univie.ac.at/10.1038/s41558-018-0119-8)</p> <p>Policy-screening scenarios = Storylines that explore the effects of</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exploratory scenario - Policy-screening scenario - Target-seeking scenario - DK (don’t know)

	<p>different policies Example: Studies that explicitly mention one or more policies whose effect are explored in the study, e.g. by varying input parameters based on the policy. (e.g.; Moser and Mußhoff, 2015, https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-9552.12114)</p> <p>If you cannot classify the model please fill this field as DK (don't know) but please add the most information as possible in the 4.2 field</p> <p>For more information see scenario type definitions below!</p>	
Scenario type (II)	If Dk in "Scenario type (I)" please provide information on the scenario from the paper.	Open answer
Scenario Structure	<p>Identify if the applied scenario is qualitative or quantitative</p> <p>Qualitative scenario (= storyline) = "Storylines, are the qualitative and descriptive component of a scenario, which create images of future worlds. They can reflect the assumptions within scenarios about the drivers of change, or they can describe the consequences or outcomes of a scenario." (Rounsvell & Metzger 2010)</p> <p>Quantitative scenario = Scenarios with numerical output (predictions) based on available models (e.g., future climate projections under different RCP scenarios)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Qualitative - Quantitative - Both
Temporal Dimension	Please identify the temporal dimension of the scenario projections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - back-casting - short-term (until 2030) - mid-term (until 2050) - long-term (until 2100)
Feedbacks	<p>Identify if feedbacks among scenarios are included in the study.</p> <p>Inclusion of feedbacks mean that in a</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - No

	step-wise process, intermediate results from the model will be used to calculate the next iteration.	
Policy	Identify if policy is included in the scenarios	- Yes - No
Management	Identify if management is included in the scenarios	- Yes - No
Drivers of Change (I)	Identify the drivers of change included in the scenarios If "other" please specify under "Drivers of Change (II)" Multiple answers are possible.	- Climate Change - Demographics - Economy - Governance - Invasive Alien Species - Land/Sea use change - Pollution - Resource extraction - Technology - Values - Other
Drivers of Change (II)	If other in "Drivers of Change (I)" please specify quoting the terminology used in the paper	Open answer
ILK	Is indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) included in the data compilation or analysis of the study (e.g. are indigenous and local people involved at any stage of the modelling/scenario process)	- Yes - No
GQL (I)	Is Good Quality of Life (GQL) included in the analysis of the study?	- Yes - No
GQL (II)	Which component of Good Quality of Life is addressed in the study? For more information on relevant sub-categories see GQL definition below!	- Material - Non-Material
NCP (I)	Are Nature's Contributions to People included in the analysis of the study?	- Yes - No
NCP (II)	Which Nature's Contribution to People (NCP) is/are addressed in the study? For more information on relevant sub-categories see NCP definition below!	- Regulating - Material - Non-Material

Pathways definitions

- Definitions following the CBD (2018) Invasive Alien Species – Guidance for interpretation of the categories on introduction pathways under the Convention on Biological Diversity
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Pathway category	Pathway subcategories following the Convention on Biological Diversity
Release in nature	Biological control, erosion control, fishery in the wild, hunting, landscape/flora/fauna improvement in the wild, introduction for conservation purposes or wildlife management, release in nature for use, other intentional release
Escape from confinement	Agriculture, aqua-/mariculture, botanical garden/zoo/aquaria, pet/aquarium/terrarium species, farmed animals, forestry, fur farms, horticulture, ornamental purpose other than horticulture, research and ex-situ breeding, live food/bait
Transport – Contaminant	Contaminant on nursery material/bait/food/plants, parasites on animals/plants, seed contaminant, timber trade, transportation of habitat material
Transport – Stowaway	Angling/fishing equipment, container/bulk, hitchhikers on airplanes/ships/boats, machinery, people and their luggage, organic packaging material, ballast water, hull fouling, vehicles
Corridor	Interconnected waterways/basins/seas, tunnels and land bridges
Unaided	Natural dispersal across borders of invasive species introduced through one of the other pathways

Model type definitions

- IPBES definitions following IPBES (2016): Summary for policymakers of the methodological assessment report on scenarios and models of biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. S. Ferrier, K. N. Ninan, P. Leadley, R. Alkemade, L. A. Acosta, H. R. Akçakaya, L. Brotons, W. W. L. Cheung, V. Christensen, K. A. Harhash, J. Kabubo-Mariara, C. Lundquist, M. Obersteiner, H. M. Pereira, G. Peterson, R. Pichs-Madruga, N. H. Ravindranath, C. Rondinini, B. A. Wintle (eds.). Secretariat of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, Bonn, Germany. 32 pages.

Model type	Defintion from the IPBES (2016) Methodological assessment
Expert-based systems	<p>“An expert is defined here as someone who has achieved a high level of knowledge on a subject through his or her life experience (Kuhnert et al., 2010), and may be a person with local knowledge or a scientist.”</p> <p>“Indigenous people, with collective knowledge of the land, sky and sea, are excellent observers and interpreters of changes in the environment. Their knowledge may offer valuable insights, complementing scientific data with chronological and landscape-specific precision and detail that is critical for verifying models and evaluating scenarios developed by scientists at much broader spatial and temporal scale.”</p>
Correlative models	<p>“Correlative models [...] use statistical methods to establish direct relationships between environmental variables and biodiversity data such as species richness, abundance or distribution. These models produce information on biodiversity patterns and responses to drivers based on empirical observations, and do not attempt to explain the mechanisms underlying those patterns and responses”</p>
Process-based models	<p>“In the literature, the terms process-based model and mechanistic model are often used as synonyms. Here, we use the term process-based for any model type with explicit implementation of ecological processes in the model (i.e. encompassing both process-based and purely mechanistic models), and we reserve the mechanistic category for the subset of models that are developed based on ecological theory only and that do not use correlative approaches at all for parameterization.”</p>
Hybrid models (combining correlative and process-based models)	<p>“Hybrid models combine correlative and process-based modelling approaches (Schurr et al., 2012) in order to represent complex, integrated systems with a focus on biophysical as well as human components (Parrott, 2011).”</p>

Scenario type definitions

- IPBES definitions following IPBES (2016): Summary for policymakers of the methodological assessment report on scenarios and models of biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. S. Ferrier, K. N. Ninan, P. Leadley, R. Alkemade, L. A. Acosta, H. R. Akçakaya, L. Brotons, W. W. L. Cheung, V. Christensen, K. A. Harhash, J. Kabubo-Mariara, C. Lundquist, M. Obersteiner, H. M. Pereira, G. Peterson, R. Pichs-Madruga, N. H. Ravindranath, C. Rondinini, B. A. Wintle (eds.). Secretariat of

the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, Bonn, Germany. 32 pages.

Model type	Defintion from the IPBES (2016) Methodological assessment
Exploratory scenarios	“Scenarios that examine a range of plausible futures based on potential trajectories of drivers – either indirect (e.g. sociopolitical, economic and technological factors) or direct (e.g. habitat conversion, climate change)”
Target-seeking scenarios	“Scenarios, in which a desired endpoint or goal is first defined and analytical techniques such as backcasting (Dreborg, 1996) are then used to search for intervention scenarios that fulfil this goal, [...]”
Policy-screening scenarios	“Scenarios, in which options for policy or management intervention are defined in advance and the relative effectiveness of these options is then evaluated through forecasting, [...]”

GQL definitions

- IPBES categorization of Good Quality of Life extracted from Shin et al. (2019) Chapter 4: Plausible futures of nature, its contributions to people and their good quality of life In: Global assessment report of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Brondízio, E. S., Settele, J., Díaz, S., Ngo, H. T. (eds). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. 168 pages. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3832074

GQL	Subcategory
Material	Food and nutritional security
	Water security
	Energy security
	Livelihood and income security
	Health
Nonmaterial	Good social relations
	Equity
	Cultural identity

Personal and physical security
Recreation and leisure
Knowledge and education
Spirituality, religion
Freedom of choice and action

NCP definitions

- IPBES categorization of Nature’s Contribution to People extracted from Brauman et al. (2020) Global trends in nature’s contribution to people. PNAS, 117, 32799-32805. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2010473117>

NCP	Subcategory	IPBES categorization published in Brauman et al. (2020)
Regulating	Habitat creation and maintenance	The formation and continued production of ecological conditions necessary or favorable for living beings important to people
	Pollination and dispersal of seeds	Animal facilitation of pollen movement and seed dispersal of beneficial organisms
	Regulation of air quality	Filtration, fixation, degradation or storage of pollutants and gasses
	Regulation of climate	Emission and sequestration of greenhouse gases, biogenic volatile organic compounds, and aerosols; biophysical feedbacks (e.g., albedo, evapotranspiration)
	Regulation of ocean acidification	Regulation by photosynthetic organisms on land and sea of atmospheric CO2 concentrations and thus seawater pH
	Regulation of freshwater quantity	Regulation of the quantity, location, and timing of the flow of surface and groundwater
	Regulation of freshwater quality	Ecosystem filtration and addition of particles, pathogens, excess nutrients, and other chemicals
	Formation and	Soil formation and long-term maintenance of soil

	protection of soils	fertility, including sediment retention and degradation or storage of pollutants
	Regulation of hazards and extreme events	Amelioration of the impacts of hazards; reduction of size or frequency of hazards
	Regulation of detrimental organisms	Regulation of pests, pathogens, predators, competitors, parasites, and potentially harmful organisms
Material	Energy	Biomass-based fuels such as biofuel crops, animal waste, and fuelwood
	Food and feed	Food and feed from wild, managed, or domesticated organisms from terrestrial, freshwater, and marine sources
	Materials and assistance	Cultivated or wild materials and direct use of living organisms for industrial, ornamental, company, transport, labor, and other uses
	Medicinal and genetic resources	Naturally derived medicinal materials; genes and genetic information
Nonmaterial	Learning and inspiration	Capabilities developed through education, knowledge acquisition, and inspiration by nature for art and technological design
	Experiences	Physically and psychologically beneficial activities, healing, relaxation, recreation, and aesthetic enjoyment based on contact with nature
	Supporting identities	The basis for religious, spiritual, and social cohesion; sense of place, purpose, belonging, or rootedness associated with the living world; narratives, myths, and rituals; satisfaction from a landscape, seascape, habitat, or species

ISO country definitions

English short name	Alpha-2 code	Alpha-3 code	Numerical
Afghanistan	AF	AFG	4
Albania	AL	ALB	8

Algeria	DZ	DZA	12
American Samoa	AS	ASM	16
Andorra	AD	AND	20
Angola	AO	AGO	24
Anguilla	AI	AIA	660
Antarctica	AQ	ATA	10
Antigua and Barbuda	AG	ATG	28
Argentina	AR	ARG	32
Armenia	AM	ARM	51
Aruba	AW	ABW	533
Australia	AU	AUS	36
Austria	AT	AUT	40
Azerbaijan	AZ	AZE	31
Bahamas (the)	BS	BHS	44
Bahrain	BH	BHR	48
Bangladesh	BD	BGD	50
Barbados	BB	BRB	52
Belarus	BY	BLR	112
Belgium	BE	BEL	56
Belize	BZ	BLZ	84
Benin	BJ	BEN	204
Bermuda	BM	BMU	60
Bhutan	BT	BTN	64
Bolivia (Plurinational State of)	BO	BOL	68
Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba	BQ	BES	535
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	BIH	70
Botswana	BW	BWA	72
Bouvet Island	BV	BVT	74
Brazil	BR	BRA	76
British Indian Ocean Territory (the)	IO	IOT	86
Brunei Darussalam	BN	BRN	96
Bulgaria	BG	BGR	100
Burkina Faso	BF	BFA	854
Burundi	BI	BDI	108
Cabo Verde	CV	CPV	132
Cambodia	KH	KHM	116
Cameroon	CM	CMR	120

Canada	CA	CAN	124
Cayman Islands (the)	KY	CYM	136
Central African Republic (the)	CF	CAF	140
Chad	TD	TCD	148
Chile	CL	CHL	152
China	CN	CHN	156
Christmas Island	CX	CXR	162
Cocos (Keeling) Islands (the)	CC	CCK	166
Colombia	CO	COL	170
Comoros (the)	KM	COM	174
Congo (the Democratic Republic of the)	CD	COD	180
Congo (the)	CG	COG	178
Cook Islands (the)	CK	COK	184
Costa Rica	CR	CRI	188
Croatia	HR	HRV	191
Cuba	CU	CUB	192
Curaçao	CW	CUW	531
Cyprus	CY	CYP	196
Czechia	CZ	CZE	203
Côte d'Ivoire	CI	CIV	384
Denmark	DK	DNK	208
Djibouti	DJ	DJI	262
Dominica	DM	DMA	212
Dominican Republic (the)	DO	DOM	214
Ecuador	EC	ECU	218
Egypt	EG	EGY	818
El Salvador	SV	SLV	222
Equatorial Guinea	GQ	GNQ	226
Eritrea	ER	ERI	232
Estonia	EE	EST	233
Eswatini	SZ	SWZ	748
Ethiopia	ET	ETH	231
Falkland Islands (the) [Malvinas]	FK	FLK	238
Faroe Islands (the)	FO	FRO	234
Fiji	FJ	FJI	242
Finland	FI	FIN	246
France	FR	FRA	250

French Guiana	GF	GUF	254
French Polynesia	PF	PYF	258
French Southern Territories (the)	TF	ATF	260
Gabon	GA	GAB	266
Gambia (the)	GM	GMB	270
Georgia	GE	GEO	268
Germany	DE	DEU	276
Ghana	GH	GHA	288
Gibraltar	GI	GIB	292
Greece	GR	GRC	300
Greenland	GL	GRL	304
Grenada	GD	GRD	308
Guadeloupe	GP	GLP	312
Guam	GU	GUM	316
Guatemala	GT	GTM	320
Guernsey	GG	GGY	831
Guinea	GN	GIN	324
Guinea-Bissau	GW	GNB	624
Guyana	GY	GUY	328
Haiti	HT	HTI	332
Heard Island and McDonald Islands	HM	HMD	334
Holy See (the)	VA	VAT	336
Honduras	HN	HND	340
Hong Kong	HK	HKG	344
Hungary	HU	HUN	348
Iceland	IS	ISL	352
India	IN	IND	356
Indonesia	ID	IDN	360
Iran (Islamic Republic of)	IR	IRN	364
Iraq	IQ	IRQ	368
Ireland	IE	IRL	372
Isle of Man	IM	IMN	833
Israel	IL	ISR	376
Italy	IT	ITA	380
Jamaica	JM	JAM	388
Japan	JP	JPN	392
Jersey	JE	JEY	832

Jordan	JO	JOR	400
Kazakhstan	KZ	KAZ	398
Kenya	KE	KEN	404
Kiribati	KI	KIR	296
Korea (the Democratic People's Republic of)	KP	PRK	408
Korea (the Republic of)	KR	KOR	410
Kuwait	KW	KWT	414
Kyrgyzstan	KG	KGZ	417
Lao People's Democratic Republic (the)	LA	LAO	418
Latvia	LV	LVA	428
Lebanon	LB	LBN	422
Lesotho	LS	LSO	426
Liberia	LR	LBR	430
Libya	LY	LBY	434
Liechtenstein	LI	LIE	438
Lithuania	LT	LTU	440
Luxembourg	LU	LUX	442
Macao	MO	MAC	446
Madagascar	MG	MDG	450
Malawi	MW	MWI	454
Malaysia	MY	MYS	458
Maldives	MV	MDV	462
Mali	ML	MLI	466
Malta	MT	MLT	470
Marshall Islands (the)	MH	MHL	584
Martinique	MQ	MTQ	474
Mauritania	MR	MRT	478
Mauritius	MU	MUS	480
Mayotte	YT	MYT	175
Mexico	MX	MEX	484
Micronesia (Federated States of)	FM	FSM	583
Moldova (the Republic of)	MD	MDA	498
Monaco	MC	MCO	492
Mongolia	MN	MNG	496
Montenegro	ME	MNE	499
Montserrat	MS	MSR	500
Morocco	MA	MAR	504

Mozambique	MZ	MOZ	508
Myanmar	MM	MMR	104
Namibia	NA	NAM	516
Nauru	NR	NRU	520
Nepal	NP	NPL	524
Netherlands (the)	NL	NLD	528
New Caledonia	NC	NCL	540
New Zealand	NZ	NZL	554
Nicaragua	NI	NIC	558
Niger (the)	NE	NER	562
Nigeria	NG	NGA	566
Niue	NU	NIU	570
Norfolk Island	NF	NFK	574
North Macedonia	MK	MKD	807
Northern Mariana Islands (the)	MP	MNP	580
Norway	NO	NOR	578
Oman	OM	OMN	512
Pakistan	PK	PAK	586
Palau	PW	PLW	585
Palestine, State of	PS	PSE	275
Panama	PA	PAN	591
Papua New Guinea	PG	PNG	598
Paraguay	PY	PRY	600
Peru	PE	PER	604
Philippines (the)	PH	PHL	608
Pitcairn	PN	PCN	612
Poland	PL	POL	616
Portugal	PT	PRT	620
Puerto Rico	PR	PRI	630
Qatar	QA	QAT	634
Romania	RO	ROU	642
Russian Federation (the)	RU	RUS	643
Rwanda	RW	RWA	646
Réunion	RE	REU	638
Saint Barthélemy	BL	BLM	652
Saint Helena, Ascension and Tristan da Cunha	SH	SHN	654
Saint Kitts and Nevis	KN	KNA	659

Saint Lucia	LC	LCA	662
Saint Martin (French part)	MF	MAF	663
Saint Pierre and Miquelon	PM	SPM	666
Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	VC	VCT	670
Samoa	WS	WSM	882
San Marino	SM	SMR	674
Sao Tome and Principe	ST	STP	678
Saudi Arabia	SA	SAU	682
Senegal	SN	SEN	686
Serbia	RS	SRB	688
Seychelles	SC	SYC	690
Sierra Leone	SL	SLE	694
Singapore	SG	SGP	702
Sint Maarten (Dutch part)	SX	SXM	534
Slovakia	SK	SVK	703
Slovenia	SI	SVN	705
Solomon Islands	SB	SLB	90
Somalia	SO	SOM	706
South Africa	ZA	ZAF	710
South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands	GS	SGS	239
South Sudan	SS	SSD	728
Spain	ES	ESP	724
Sri Lanka	LK	LKA	144
Sudan (the)	SD	SDN	729
Suriname	SR	SUR	740
Svalbard and Jan Mayen	SJ	SJM	744
Sweden	SE	SWE	752
Switzerland	CH	CHE	756
Syrian Arab Republic (the)	SY	SYR	760
Taiwan (Province of China)	TW	TWN	158
Tajikistan	TJ	TJK	762
Tanzania, the United Republic of	TZ	TZA	834
Thailand	TH	THA	764
Timor-Leste	TL	TLS	626
Togo	TG	TGO	768
Tokelau	TK	TKL	772

Tonga	TO	TON	776
Trinidad and Tobago	TT	TTO	780
Tunisia	TN	TUN	788
Turkey	TR	TUR	792
Turkmenistan	TM	TKM	795
Turks and Caicos Islands (the)	TC	TCA	796
Tuvalu	TV	TUV	798
Uganda	UG	UGA	800
Ukraine	UA	UKR	804
United Arab Emirates (the)	AE	ARE	784
United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (the)	GB	GBR	826
United States Minor Outlying Islands (the)	UM	UMI	581
United States of America (the)	US	USA	840
Uruguay	UY	URY	858
Uzbekistan	UZ	UZB	860
Vanuatu	VU	VUT	548
Venezuela (Bolivarian Republic of)	VE	VEN	862
Viet Nam	VN	VNM	704
Virgin Islands (British)	VG	VGB	92
Virgin Islands (U.S.)	VI	VIR	850
Wallis and Futuna	WF	WLF	876
Western Sahara*	EH	ESH	732
Yemen	YE	YEM	887
Zambia	ZM	ZMB	894
Zimbabwe	ZW	ZWE	716
Åland Islands	AX	ALA	248

Model features

Model extent. Most models in the context of invasive alien species were applied at the Sub-national scale (41 per cent of papers), followed by the national (20 per cent), global (15 per cent), international (10 per cent), continental (7 per cent) or protected areas (3 per cent). For 3 per cent of the papers the model type was not stated.

Model type and outputs. Most papers used correlative models (57 per cent of 781 observations), followed by process-based models (33 per cent), hybrid models (8 per cent) and expert-based systems (1 per cent).

Other model features. Most models applied to invasive alien species focused on species distributions (61 per cent), followed by species abundance (19 per cent), impacts (9 per cent), survival and growth and life cycle (6 per cent), species richness (4 per cent), and intraspecific diversity (including genetic or trait diversity; 1 per cent).

Scenario features

Scenario type and structure. Most papers focused on exploratory scenarios (87 per cent of papers), followed by policy-screening (7 per cent) and target-seeking scenarios (6 per cent). In most papers, scenarios were quantitative (82 per cent) as opposed to qualitative (9 per cent) or both quantitative and qualitative scenarios (8 per cent).

Scenario drivers. Most papers focused on one scenario driver (77 per cent of 778 papers), with combinations of two (17 per cent) or three (6 per cent) different types of drivers being considered in most of the remaining papers. Climate change was the most commonly included driver (48 per cent of all observations; 1012 occurrences), followed by drivers pertaining to invasive alien species management (12 per cent). The least represented drivers pertained to the anthropogenic system and included: demographics, governance, pollution, resource extraction, values and technology, with representation of less than 2 per cent each.

Other scenario attributes. In most cases the papers focused on forecasting in the long-term (until 2050-2100; 42 per cent of 778 papers), followed by short-term (until 2030; 30 per cent) and mid-term (until 2030-2050; 18 per cent). Backcasting was the focus of just 8 per cent papers.

Expert-based models have been used to assess potential future trends in alien species richness and distribution (Dehnen-Schmutz et al., 2018; Gallardo et al., 2016; Peyton et al., 2019, 2020; Swart & Robinson, 2019; Tsiamis et al., 2020) or to assess potential important drivers and pathways of alien species (Essl et al., 2020; Lenzner et al., 2020). Methods used in expert-based systems include horizon scanning for future invasive alien species (Lucy et al., 2020; Peyton et al., 2019, 2020; Rayon-Viña et al., 2019; Roy et al., 2014, 2017; Vaz et al., 2021), feasibility of management (Booy et al., 2020), and surveys addressing complex issues on biological invasions directed to experts (Dehnen-Schmutz et al., 2018; Essl et al., 2020; Lenzner et al., 2020).

Correlative models include species distribution models (Elith & Leathwick, 2009; Guisan et al., 2006; Václavík & Meentemeyer, 2009), general dissimilarity models (Ferrier et al., 2007; Latombe et al., 2017), and other types of regression modelling approaches. Species distribution models, which correlate species occurrences (i.e., presence-absence or abundance data) to environmental and socioeconomic variables, are among the most frequently used correlative approaches for modelling potential current and future alien species richness, abundance, and distribution (Elith & Leathwick, 2009; Guisan et al., 2006; Santamarina et al., 2019; Srivastava et al., 2018; Václavík & Meentemeyer, 2009). Species distribution models have been applied across different spatial and temporal scales, taxonomic groups and realms (Bellard et al., 2013, 2013; Dullinger et al., 2017; Kolar & Lodge, 2001). The outputs from species distribution models are frequently translated into management and decision-making strategies

(Fernandes et al., 2019; Santamarina et al., 2019; Vicente et al., 2016). Other correlative modelling approaches that have been frequently applied (e.g., in macroecology) aim to establish causal relationships between drivers (e.g., climate change, land- and sea-use) and alien species richness and distributions (Capinha et al., 2018; Jarnevich et al., 2006; Nobis et al., 2009) or compositional similarity (Baird et al., 2019; Kortz & Magurran, 2019; Latombe et al., 2018; Vicente et al., 2016). In contrast, to species distribution models, these approaches do not use species occurrence datasets and are generally less computationally intensive.

A limitation to correlative models is the assumption that (historic) statistical relationships remain constant in the future and using proxy variables based on historic relationships only enables underlying processes to be inferred based on correlation not causation (Blackburn et al., 2020). For example, variables related to propagule or colonization pressure are often substituted with variables of socioeconomic activities or societal development in the absence of direct measurements. However, such proxy variables do not enable the differentiation of underlying processes such as competitive interactions between native and alien species or habitat and microclimatic effects on establishment success (Blackburn et al., 2020; Dawson et al., 2017; Dyer et al., 2017; Essl et al., 2019). Therefore, the relationships derived from the models do not capture all relevant aspects shaping future species richness and distribution patterns because key processes and mechanisms are not explicitly included. It has been argued that predictions of alien species richness derived from these methods only have medium to low accuracy and should not be extended beyond the original study region where the model has been developed (Capinha et al., 2018). However, others have shown that transferability across regions is appropriate in some circumstances Liu et al., 2020). Correlative models of invasive alien species calibrated from data in native ranges can in some cases accurately predict the distribution of species within invaded regions (Petitpierre et al., 2012) but in other cases they fail (Early & Sax, 2014).

Though frequently applied, correlative, regression based models (including species distribution models) ignore one basic assumption that is not usually fulfilled by invasive alien species that the species is in equilibrium with environmental conditions (Capinha et al., 2018). Given that many alien species introductions are very recent (*Figure 1.1* and *chapter 2, Figure 2.4*) and are still expanding, this assumption is unlikely to be valid and ultimately leads to underestimations of potential future distribution (Pompe et al., 2008). Additionally, pathways of introduction are not generally included within the models. Furthermore, the robustness of the predictions from the model depends on the source of the environmental data independent of the chosen predictor variables (Datta et al., 2020). Strongly underpinning models with biological knowledge, rather than relying solely on distributional data, considerably improves the projections of regional and global potential distributions (Chapman et al., 2019).

Process-based models for future predictions are currently less developed for biological invasions than in other fields, but a mechanistic understanding of the biological invasion process is essential to understand and manage ecological systems (Buchadas et al., 2017; Hall et al., 2021; Portela et al., 2020). For long-term projections, mechanistic models are more robust than correlative models because they integrate systems dynamics and can also include adaptation and mitigation strategies (IPBES, 2016; Sitzia et al., 2018; Walther et al., 2009). However, process-based models are much harder to parameterize as they are “built from scratch” and are more computationally intensive. Process-based

models in invasion biology have been applied to single species (e.g., *Dreissena polymorpha* (Glaser et al., 2009); forest pathogens (Dietze & Matthes, 2014)), to understand the influence of changes in specific drivers (e.g., Seebens et al., 2019), and to assess changes at different biological invasion stages (e.g., Belmaker et al., 2009; Liebhold et al., 2017; Lustig et al., 2019; Seebens et al., 2018).

Hybrid models combine species distribution models with mechanistic population models (e.g., D. Chapman et al., 2017; Gamliel et al., 2020; Klonner et al., 2019). The advantage of these models over species distribution models is the increased accuracy of predictions of potential alien species distributions because of the inclusion of realistic population and spread dynamics based on individual species life history traits (Gamliel et al., 2020; Klonner et al., 2019). Hybrid models have been applied to inform the management of invasive alien species (Buchadas et al., 2017).

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